

Russia-affiliated scholars publishing about internationalisation of higher education

A quantitative investigation based on Scopus

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Objective of this research note

Outline trends in the publication record of Russia-affiliated scholars writing about internationalisation of higher education and publishing their work in established scholarly journals

Operationalisation of the objective

Rely on the Scopus API to search for all articles published:

- **between 2011 and 2024**
- in the following **subject area 'SOCI'**
- matching in either the title, the abstract, or the author-provided article keywords the following string: **'higher education'**
 - considering other criteria for narrowing further the number of results in subsequent steps
- in any Scopus-indexed journal
 - considering the option to limit results to top ranked journals (e.g. Q1 and Q2)

Additional notes clarifying some of these choices

- **Why set 2011 as the start date?**

- **data availability:** according to the official Scopus website, journal CiteScore data are effectively available only starting with 2011; as CiteScore is used for filtering Q1 and Q2 publications, this criteria could scarcely be consistently applied retroactively (“the first journal metric values for CiteScore are available for 2011” - https://service.elsevier.com/app/answers/detail/a_id/29859/)
 - **relevance:** the focus is on policies favouring internationalisation of higher education that gained traction in Russia mostly in the 2010s
 - **pragmatic considerations:** in previous years, the number of publications focused on higher education by Russia-affiliated scholars is anyway negligible
- **Why set only SOCI as the subject area?**
 - **pragmatic considerations:** a separate test including also “ECON” and “ARTS” has been conducted; the number of additional unique matches was limited, and often less relevant
 - **clarity:** an explicit focus on social sciences Scopus-indexed journals enhances clarity in the case selection
 - **Why rely only on “higher education” as keyword?**
 - **pragmatic considerations:** additional contiguous keywords, such as “university”, brought in a large number of spurious matching; domain-specific keywords (e.g. “Bologna process”) may have skewed results; ultimately, if an article really focuses on internationalisation of higher education it is strongly expected that it will use that expression in either title, abstract, or user-selected keywords
 - **Why only journal publications, and not e.g. book chapters?**
 - **pragmatic considerations:** focusing on journal articles allows to differentiate publications based on ranking

Data retrieval

The data was downloaded from Scopus API in January 2025 via api.elsevier.com and www.scopus.com.

See:

- Scopus Use Policies
- Scopus Attribution Guide

Differentiate articles

Articles are differentiated based on a set of criteria:

- articles with at least an author with a Russian affiliation?
- articles published in Q1 and Q2 journals VS all Scopus-indexed publications
- articles that are specifically about *internationalisation* of higher education, base on a narrow or slightly broader set of criteria.

The same analysis and graphs will be reproduced based on each set of criteria.

Table 1: Scopus-indexed journal articles mentioning higher education in either title, abstract, or keyword

year	All	No Russian affiliation	Russian affiliation	Russian affiliation share
2011	4073	4057	16	0.39%
2012	4399	4341	58	1.32%
2013	4991	4941	50	1.00%
2014	5450	5328	122	2.24%
2015	6126	5837	289	4.72%
2016	6481	6134	347	5.35%
2017	7115	6802	313	4.40%
2018	8287	7829	458	5.53%
2019	9915	9373	542	5.47%
2020	11552	11014	538	4.66%
2021	12404	11894	510	4.11%
2022	13497	13041	456	3.38%
2023	14666	14200	466	3.18%
2024	18532	18142	390	2.10%

Table 2: Q1 and Q2 Scopus-indexed journal articles mentioning higher education in either title, abstract, or keyword.

year	All	No Russian affiliation	Russian affiliation	Russian affiliation share
2011	1595	1594	1	0.06%
2012	1797	1788	9	0.50%
2013	2130	2124	6	0.28%
2014	2143	2134	9	0.42%
2015	2376	2362	14	0.59%
2016	2608	2595	13	0.50%
2017	2994	2956	38	1.27%
2018	3672	3588	84	2.29%
2019	4317	4139	178	4.12%
2020	5426	5169	257	4.74%
2021	6197	5901	296	4.78%
2022	7350	7076	274	3.73%
2023	8556	8267	289	3.38%
2024	11344	11117	227	2.00%

Two approaches for keeping only articles about *internationalisation* of higher education

Analysis based only on articles that explicitly refer to internationalisation of higher education (narrower criteria)

In order to capture only articles that explicitly focus on internationalisation of higher education, this section is based only on articles that match the following criteria:

- the full string “internationali(s|z)ation of higher education” is present in either title or abstract
- the author-provided keywords include both “higher education” and “internationali(s|z)ation”

This leads to a significantly reduced set of publications.

Table 3: Total number of publications based on the narrow criteria

Property	Value
Total publications	1919
Publications with Russia-affiliated authors	70

Table 4: Institutions with most publications and most citations based on narrower criteria

Publications	Cited	affilname	affiliation-country
16	816	University of Toronto	Canada
40	772	The Education University of Hong Kong	China
13	733	Boston College	United States
16	517	The University of British Columbia	Canada
28	463	The University of Hong Kong	Hong Kong
11	427	The University of Queensland	Australia
17	378	UCL Institute of Education	United Kingdom
6	358	University of South Australia	Australia
13	352	Monash University	Australia
6	347	Korea University	South Korea

Universities with most publications (narrower criteria)

Number of publications about internationalisation of higher education

Counting relevant social sciences publications in Scopus-indexed journals

* 'Russian affiliation' attributed if at least one author is affiliated with a Russia-based institution

Table 5: Most cited affiliations in Russia (narrower definition)

Affiliation	affiliation-city	PublicationsCited	
HSE University	Moscow	8	82
RUDN University	Moscow	5	34
Ural Federal University	Yekaterinburg	4	28
Russian Presidential Academy of National Economy and Public Administration	Moscow	4	26
Moscow State Institute of International Relations (MGIMO)	Moscow	5	23
Far Eastern Federal University	Vladivostok	2	23
Plekhanov Russian University of Economics	Moscow	2	20
Siberian Federal University	Krasnoyarsk	3	20
Saint Petersburg State University	Saint Petersburg	5	18
University of Tyumen	Tyumen	1	16

Include also articles that mention concepts that are contiguous to internationalisation of higher education (broader criteria)

Rather than keeping only articles that refer to “internationalisation of higher education”, the following section includes also articles that, besides “higher education”, *also* has one of the following keywords in either title, abstract, or author-given keywords. This list of keywords has been inductively derived from the most frequent terms that appeared in the abstracts meeting the narrower definition.

Table 6: Selected keywords relevant to internationalisation of higher education

keywords
internationalisation
internationalization
foreign students
foreign language
academic mobility
student mobility
international students
bologna process

keywords

international education
export of education
world-class universities

Table 7: Scopus-indexed journal articles mentioning higher education (broader definition)

year	All	No Russian affiliation	Russian affiliation	Russian affiliation share
2011	240	238	2	0.83%
2012	255	251	4	1.57%
2013	332	331	1	0.30%
2014	339	327	12	3.54%
2015	373	338	35	9.38%
2016	462	409	53	11.47%
2017	409	374	35	8.56%
2018	532	459	73	13.72%
2019	630	539	91	14.44%
2020	720	649	71	9.86%
2021	771	689	82	10.64%
2022	833	780	53	6.36%
2023	972	915	57	5.86%
2024	1216	1179	37	3.04%

Number of publications about internationalisation of higher education Counting relevant social sciences publications in Scopus-indexed journals

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Number of publications about internationalisation of higher education

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